

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Meteorological influence on particulate matter levels: A case study of Bonpara, Natore

Md. Zakir Hossain Khan *, Md. Abu Faysal Rana, Md. Nurullah and Rakibul Hasan Rakib

Department of Civil Engineering, Bangladesh Army University of Engineering and Technology, Natore-6431.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 25(03), 1632-1644

Publication history: Received on 14 February 2025; revised on 21 March 2025; accepted on 24 March 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.3.0916>

Abstract

This study analyzed PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels in Bonpara, examining their correlation with meteorological factors. Data was collected from 10 selected stations within a 3 km radius of the Bonpara Bypass, covering three directions: northeast, southeast, and west. Measurements were taken at 500m, 1km, and 3km from the center during both dry and wet seasons, with each station providing 14 data points. Results showed the highest particulate matter concentrations at the Bonpara Bypass center, particularly during the dry season. Average PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels were 156 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 169 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, exceeding Bangladesh Gazette standards (65 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5} and 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM₁₀). In contrast, stations with less traffic recorded 95 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (PM_{2.5}) and 104 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (PM₁₀). The study attributes this to heavy vehicular movement in the bypass area.

In the wet season, frequent rainfall and higher humidity reduced particulate matter levels. At the bypass center, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ dropped to 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 56 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while other stations recorded 35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 42 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, staying within standard limits. Wind direction also played a key role, with higher PM concentrations downwind of the bypass. Additionally, construction at Stations 07 and 08 in the dry season resulted in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels of 113 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 126 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively, exceeding the PM_{2.5} standard. The study highlights the impact of humidity, rainfall, and human activities on air quality. Expanding monitoring locations and raising public awareness are essential to mitigate PM pollution in Bonpara.

Keywords: Air pollution; Construction dust; Traffic dust; Sustainable development; Environmental pollution

1. Introduction

The pollution of air has been one of the biggest issues of eco-environmental problems in the world [1]. There are five different types of air pollutants, such as carbon monoxide (CO), ground-level ozone (O₃), nitric oxide (NO), Sulphur dioxide (SO₂), and particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) [2]. Particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) is one of the alarming issues for the world because Human health issues are associated with particulate matter [3]. Several studies have shown that both particle size has a significant negative impact on human health [4]. The last 20 years have seen a decline in air quality which is frequently attributed to the exponential growth in anthropogenic activity brought on by increasing urbanization which is mostly over more densely populated urban areas [5]. Major cities in Bangladesh are worried about air pollution [6].

Many research has highlighted the significant impact of meteorological factors on air pollution levels. A study by demonstrated a strong correlation between wind speed, wind direction, and precipitation patterns with variations in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations which These findings underscore the importance of considering meteorological conditions when assessing and mitigating air pollution [7]. Particulate matter emissions are further exacerbated by an increase in vehicle traffic where older or poorly maintained cars are more harmful [8]. In The cities of Europe, automobile traffic increases PM concentration, and traffic-generated emissions make for over half of all PM emissions

* Corresponding author: Zakir Hossain Khan

and automobile traffic accounts for almost 80% of PM emissions in London, UK, and 66.5% in Athens, Greece [8]. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ particles are typically released from sources like automobiles, material handling, crushing and grinding operations, and windblown dust [9]. A study conducted in Taiwan which showed that the PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ concentrations increased during an Asian dust storm (ADS) and the PM₁₀ concentrations were approximately 2–3 times higher than when there were no ADS [10].

Building upon these existing studies, this research aims to investigate the specific relationship between meteorological factors and PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations in the vicinity of Bonpara Bypass Bus Stop, Natore. By analysing data on wind speed, wind direction, precipitation, and PM levels, this study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing air quality in this region. The findings of this research will have important implications for developing effective air pollution mitigation strategies and improving public health outcomes in Natore and other regions facing similar challenges. The discharge of particulate matter into the atmosphere is mostly caused by industrial emissions from nearby companies and continuous building constructions produce dust where particularly if appropriate dust control measures are not taken. Objective of this research was to monitor particulate matter levels in the ambient air of the Bonpara region, analyze their variations across different locations, and assess the impact of meteorological factors on their dispersion.

Ecosystems are exposed to multiple air pollutants simultaneously, but it can be difficult to assess the overall impact of air pollution on organisms in a particular ecosystem [11]. But these pollutions have a big adverse impact on the ecosystems as well. Air pollution effects on the physiology, growth and reproduction [12].

2. Methodology

Study location was at Bonpara Bypass, Baraigram, Natore District, Rajshahi Division. The bus stop is in Majgaon, Baraigram Upazila-6430, Natore district, Rajshahi Division. Samples were collected from the Bonpara Bypass and around a 3km radius from the center of the Bypass. Collected data were in three directions from the center. They are North-East (N-E), South-East (S-E), and West direction. In each direction, PM measurement was conducted at an interval of 500m, 1km, and 3km respectively. The area of Bonpara is 6.92 sq. km and the position on the world map is 24° 17' 39.12" north latitude and 89° 4' 52.32" east longitude. Study location is shown in figure 1. During dry season, PM measurement was conducted from 3 February 2024 to 10 February 2024, and during wet season measurement was conducted from 5 September 2024 to 11 September 2024. The sample collection time was around 30 minutes in every stations.

Figure 1 Location of Study Area (Baraigram, Natore)

PM measurements were taken from 10 selected stations in dry season and wet season as shown in figure 2. 1. PM measurement station 01 was in Bonpara Bypass (24° 17' 53.8296", 89° 4' 48.5652"), station 02 was 500m west of the

Bypass ($24^{\circ} 17' 54.3228''$, $89^{\circ} 4' 31.0152''$), station 03 was 1km west of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 17' 55.0752''$, $89^{\circ} 4' 12.486''$), station 04 was 3km west of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 17' 59.3196''$, $89^{\circ} 2' 57.7392''$), station 05 was 500m North-East of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 1' 48.65808''$, $89^{\circ} 4' 58.908''$), station 06 was 1km North-East of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 18' 20.3292''$, $89^{\circ} 5' 11.4612''$), station 07 was 3km North-East of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 19' 12.0648''$, $89^{\circ} 5' 46.3092''$), station 08 was 500m South-East of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 17' 44.6604''$, $89^{\circ} 5' 3.2496''$), station 09 is 1km South-East of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 17' 37.1652''$, $89^{\circ} 5' 21.0228''$), and station 10 was 3km South-East of the Bypass ($24^{\circ} 17' 22.2108''$, $89^{\circ} 6' 30.3984''$). Total 140 samples were taken from selected 10 stations.

Figure 2 Sampling Locations

Dust particle meter SR-516 was used for PM measurement during study period, which could detect 1.0um, 2.5um, and 10um particle size dust quantity concentration, temperature, humidity and AQI level. With 3.2-inch TFT full-color display, automatic and manual measurement, real-time date and time, rechargeable lithium battery or separate external USB power supply, sensor life was about 8000 hours. Sampler is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Dust Particle Meter SR-516

All the data was collected from the indicated Station were processed and analyzed using Microsoft Office Excel 2021. Arch GIS software was used as well for attaching the study areas.

3. Result and Discussion

The Bonpara Bypass, particularly at Sampling Station 1, experiences a consistently high volume of traffic. This route serves as a crucial passage for vehicles traveling from greater Rajshahi and Pabna district towards the capital, Dhaka, making it a key focal point for this study. Additionally, ongoing construction activities were observed at Stations 07 and 08 during the study period. Figures 4 to 10 illustrate the PM concentration in the air during the dry season throughout the study period, while Figures 11 to 17 depict the PM concentration in the air during the wet season.

Figure 4 illustrates that on Day 01 of the dry season, the wind direction was from west to east. The average PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations in the center and upwind direction were 64 µg/m³ and 76 µg/m³, respectively. In the downwind direction, the average PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations increased to 102 µg/m³ and 112 µg/m³. A significant rise in PM concentration was observed along the wind direction. The average humidity recorded was 49%.

Figure 4 Day 1 (Dry Season)

Figure 5 illustrates that on Day 02 of the dry season, the wind direction remained west to east. The average PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations in the center and upwind direction were 83 µg/m³ and 91 µg/m³, respectively. In the downwind direction, these values measured 96 µg/m³ and 109 µg/m³. The recorded average humidity for the day was 55%.

Figure 5 Day 2 (Dry Season)

Figure 6 illustrates that on Day 03 of the dry season, the wind direction shifted from northwest to southeast. The average $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentrations in the center and upwind direction were $82 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $95 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively, while in the downwind direction, they measured $91 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $102 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The recorded average humidity for the day was 53%.

Figure 6 Day 3 (Dry Season)

Figure 7 illustrates that on day 04 of the dry season, the wind blew from the South-West towards the North-East. The mean concentrations of $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} measured from the center to the upwind direction were $88 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $101 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. In contrast, the average $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} levels in the downwind direction were higher, at $122 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $133 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The day's average humidity was recorded at 46%.

Figure 7 day 4 (Dry Season)

Figure 8 demonstrates that on day 05 of the dry season, the wind originated from the North-West and moved towards the South-East. The average $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentrations from the center to the upwind direction were $66 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and

74 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. In the downwind direction, the average concentrations increased, reaching 86 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and 98 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{10} . The overall humidity for the day was recorded at 51%.

Figure 8 Day 5 (Dry Season)

Figure 9 depicts that on day 06 of the dry season, the wind was blowing from the West to the East. The average concentrations of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} measured from the center to the upwind direction were 76 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 88 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. In the downwind direction, the average levels increased, with $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ at 96 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and PM_{10} at 107 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The day's overall humidity was noted to be 45%.

Figure 9 Day 6 (Dry Season)

Figure 10 illustrates that on day 07 of the dry season, the wind direction was from West to East. The average concentrations of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} in the upwind direction from the center were 78 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 89 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. In the downwind direction, the average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} levels rose to 94 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 106 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The overall humidity for the day was recorded at 54%.

Figure 10 Day 7 (Dry Season)

Figure 11 shows that on day 01 of the Wet season, the wind was blowing from the South-West to the North-East. The average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measured from the center to the upwind direction were 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 37 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. In the downwind direction, the average concentrations increased to 36 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5} and 43 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM₁₀. A noticeable increase in particulate matter levels was observed along the wind's path. The recorded average humidity was 81%, and it was a rainy day during the sampling period.

Figure 11 Day 1 (Wet Season)

Figure 12 illustrates that on day 02 of the Wet season, the wind direction was from the North-West to the South-East. The average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measured from the center to the upwind direction were 32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 39 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. In the downwind direction, the concentrations increased to 43 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5} and 51 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM₁₀. The average humidity recorded for the day was 87%, and it was another rainy day during the sampling.

Figure 12 Day 2 (Wet Season)

Figure 13 demonstrates that on day 03 of the Wet season, the wind was blowing from the South-West to the North-East. The average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measured from the center to the upwind direction were 38 µg/m³ and 43 µg/m³, respectively. In the downwind direction, the concentrations slightly increased to 42 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5} and 49 µg/m³ for PM₁₀. The recorded average humidity for the day was 79%.

Figure 13 Day 3 (Wet Season)

Figure 14 illustrates that on day 04 of the Wet season, the wind was blowing from the North-West to the South-East. The average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measured from the center to the upwind direction were 35 µg/m³ and 41 µg/m³, respectively. In the downwind direction, the average concentrations for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ were 35 µg/m³ and 42 µg/m³. While the average PM_{2.5} levels remained the same in both the upwind and downwind directions, the average PM₁₀ levels were higher in the direction of the wind. The recorded average humidity for the day was 81%.

Figure 14 Day 4 (Wet Season)

Figure 15 shows that on day 05 of the Wet season, the wind was blowing from the South-West to the North-East. The average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measured from the center to the upwind direction were 33 µg/m³ and 39 µg/m³, respectively. In the downwind direction, the concentrations increased slightly, with PM_{2.5} at 35 µg/m³ and PM₁₀ at 43 µg/m³. The recorded average humidity for the day was 88%, and it was another rainy day during the sampling period.

Figure 15 Day 5 (Wet Season)

Figure 16 depicts that on day 06 of the Wet season, the wind was blowing from the South-West to the North-East. The average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measured from the center to the upwind direction were 32 µg/m³ and 40 µg/m³, respectively. In the downwind direction, the concentrations increased to 37 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5} and 44 µg/m³ for PM₁₀. The recorded average humidity for the day was 78%.

Figure 16 Day 6 (Wet Season)

Figure 17 shows that on day 07 of the Wet season, the wind was blowing from the South-West to the North-East. The average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measured from the center to the upwind direction were 32 µg/m³ and 39 µg/m³, respectively. In the downwind direction, the concentrations increased to 36 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5} and 43 µg/m³ for PM₁₀. Particulate matter levels were higher in the direction of the wind. The recorded average humidity for the day was 88%, and it was yet another rainy day during the sampling period.

Figure 17 Day 7 (Wet Season)

Construction of a building took place during the dry season at stations 07 and 08. These construction sites exhibited significantly higher levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ compared to other locations, except station 01. The PM_{2.5} levels exceeded the standard value of 65 µg/m³, as specified by the Bangladesh Air Pollution Control Rules 2022. Construction activities are varied in their sources of air pollution, often releasing particulate matter, gases, and other pollutants into the atmosphere. Some of the common ways in which construction work contributes to air pollution [2]. Activities like excavation, demolition, and material handling generate significant dust emissions, which are major contributors to both coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀) and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) [13]. In India, the primary sources of ambient

particulate matter pollution include biomass burning for household and commercial use, industrial emissions, and construction activities [14].

The research revealed that the particulate matter levels were higher at the center of the Bonpara Bypass during both the dry and wet seasons. Data collected indicated that the average $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentrations at the center of the Bonpara Bypass were $156 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $169 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively, during the dry season. In contrast, at all other stations, the average $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} values were approximately $95 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $104 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. During the wet season, the average $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} values at the center of the Bonpara Bypass decreased to $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $56 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. Outside of the Bypass, the average concentrations of $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} across all stations were around $35 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $42 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The Bonpara Bypass experienced heavy traffic activity, while other locations had little to no traffic activity. Traffic activities are the cause of the elevated level of Particulate matter [15]. The road transportation system has direct relationship to air pollution such as Vehicle speed, mileage, age of vehicles and the average speed during peak hours [16].

The study found that $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentrations in Bonpara were much higher in areas downwind of the Bonpara Bypass, highlighting the significant influence of wind direction on the dispersion of particulate matter. When the wind originated from the bypass, elevated levels of both $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} were detected in its path. Particulate matter concentration can either increase or decrease based on the direction and speed of the wind. Higher wind speeds create stronger turbulence, which enhances the dispersion of pollutants, allowing them to spread more effectively [7]. Wind direction, in addition to wind speed, plays a crucial role in determining PM concentrations, as it affects the spatial distribution of pollution sources and the movement of air pollutants [17].

The study observed that during the dry season, when humidity levels are lower, $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentrations tend to be higher. However, in the wet season, when rainfall is frequent and humidity is higher, the levels of $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} are generally lower [15]. Precipitation has been identified as one of the main natural mechanisms in the majority of places for lowering PM levels [18].

In recent years, several studies have highlighted the link between fine particulate matter and various health issues, emphasizing the harmful effects of its toxic components. Health issues, including respiratory symptoms and reduced lung function, can result from exposure to fine particulate matter [19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. Amidst the environmental challenges in Bangladesh and the swift, unplanned urbanization, many studies have been carried out on air pollution. One notable study examined air pollution levels in Dhaka during the winter of 1995-1996 [24]. From 1996 to 2003, air quality evaluations in Chittagong, Bangladesh, indicated moderate pollution levels, marked by elevated concentrations of suspended particulate matter. The results also pointed to the likelihood of more severe pollution in the years to come [25]. In 2022, Bangladesh implemented its most recent legislation addressing air pollution [26]. The regulations governing air pollution in Bangladesh are outlined in the Air Pollution Control Rules, Bangladesh. According to the country's air quality standards (S.R.O. 255-law/2022), the annual average concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ in ambient air must not exceed $35 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while the daily average should remain below $65 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Similarly, for PM_{10} , the annual average should stay under $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with the daily average not exceeding $150 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

4. Conclusion

The Bonpara Bypass has been witnessing escalating levels of particulate matter. The study indicated that $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentrations at the bypass were significantly higher compared to locations 500 meters, 1 kilometer, and 3 kilometers away in the west, northeast, and southeast directions. This rise in particulate matter near the bypass is primarily attributed to transportation, with vehicle emissions contributing substantially to the elevated PM levels. However, areas located 500 meters, 1 kilometer, and 3 kilometers from the bypass in the mentioned directions showed lower PM concentrations, due to less traffic and the presence of more agricultural land. Particulate matter concentrations are notably higher in the direction of the wind, as dust, pollutants, and other particles are carried by the wind. Consequently, PM levels were higher downwind of the bypass, while areas upwind exhibited lower levels. Wind direction plays a critical role in the dispersion and distribution of particulate matter.

In addition, construction sites near Bonpara also had elevated levels of $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} , surpassing other locations, with activities such as excavation and material handling contributing to increased particulate matter. During the dry season, when humidity levels are lower, PM concentrations tend to rise. Conversely, in the wet season, frequent rainfall and higher humidity help reduce PM levels. To improve air quality in the Bonpara Bypass area, enhanced traffic control, cleaner vehicles, and better traffic management strategies are necessary to curb PM pollution

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Zhang, B., Jiao, L., Xu, G., Zhao, S., Tang, X., Zhou, Y., & Gong, C. (2017). Influences of wind and precipitation on different-sized particulate matter concentrations (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5-10}). *Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics*, 130(3), 383-392. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00703-017-0526-9>
- [2] Hossain, M. L., Roy, S. C., Bepari, M. C., & Begum, B. A. (2019). Study of air quality at one of the world's most densely populated city Dhaka and its suburban areas. *Journal of Bangladesh Academy of Sciences*, 43(1), 59-66. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jbas.v43i1.42234>
- [3] Gillies, J. A., Gertler, A. W., Sagebiel, J. C., & Dippel, W. A. (2001). On-road particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) emissions in the Sepulveda tunnel, Los Angeles, California. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 35(6), 1054-1063. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es991320p>
- [4] Dockery, D. W. (1993). Epidemiologic study design for investigating respiratory health effects of complex air pollution mixtures. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 101(suppl 4), 187-191. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.93101s4187>
- [5] Gupta, A., Moniruzzaman, M., Hande, A., Rousta, I., Olafsson, H., & Mondal, K. K. (2020). Estimation of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) concentration and its variation over urban sites in Bangladesh. *SN Applied Sciences*, 2(12). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-03829-1>
- [6] Begum, B. A., Biswas, S. K., & Hopke, P. K. (2008). Assessment of trends and present ambient concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*, 1(3), 125-133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11869-008-0018-7>
- [7] Tian, G., Qiao, Z., & Xu, X. (2014). Characteristics of particulate matter (PM₁₀) and its relationship with meteorological factors during 2001–2012 in Beijing. *Environmental Pollution*, 192, 266-274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2014.04.036>
- [8] Srimuruganandam, B., & Shiva Nagendra, S. M. (2010). Analysis and interpretation of particulate matter – PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM₁ emissions from the heterogeneous traffic near an urban roadway. *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, 1(3), 184-194. <https://doi.org/10.5094/apr.2010.024>
- [9] Pfeiffer, R. (2015). Sampling for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} particulates. *Agronomy Monographs*, 227-245. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronmonogr47.c11>
- [10] Chen, S., Hsieh, L., Kao, M., Lin, W., Huang, K., & Lin, C. (2004). Characteristics of particles sampled in southern Taiwan during the Asian dust storm periods in 2000 and 2001. *Atmospheric Environment*, 38(35), 5925-5934. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2004.07.006>
- [11] Lovett, G. M., Tear, T. H., Evers, D. C., Findlay, S. E., Cosby, B. J., Dunscomb, J. K., Driscoll, C. T., & Weathers, K. C. (2009). Effects of air pollution on ecosystems and biological diversity in the eastern United States. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1162(1), 99-135. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2009.04153.x>
- [12] Taylor, G. E., Johnson, D. W., & Andersen, C. P. (1994). Air pollution and forest ecosystems: A regional to global perspective. *Ecological Applications*, 4(4), 662-689. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1941999>
- [13] Cheriyian, D., Choi, J. H. (2020). A review of research on particulate matter pollution in the construction industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 254, 120077, 77-87
- [14] Guttikunda SK, Goel R, Pant P. (2014). Nature of air pollution, emission sources, and management in the Indian cities. *Atmos Environ* 2014, 95, 501–510
- [15] Owolabi, T. O., Ajayi, O. O., & Olofu, D. A. (2024). Assessment of air pollution levels from a building construction site on Lagos Island. *ABUAD Journal of Engineering Research and Development (AJERD)*, 7(2), 229-235. <https://doi.org/10.53982/ajerd.2024.0702.22-j>
- [16] Shrivastava, R., S. Neeta and G. Geeta. (2013). Air pollution due to road transportation in India: A review on assessment and reduction strategies. *J. Env. Res. Develop.*, 8(1):69–77

- [17] Guerra, S. A., Lane, D. D., Marotz, G. A., Carter, R. E., Hohl, C. M., & Baldauf, R. W. (2006). Effects of wind direction on coarse and fine particulate matter concentrations in southeast Kansas. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association*, 56(11), 1525-1531. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10473289.2006.10464559>
- [18] Duhanyan, N., & Roustan, Y. (2011). Below-cloud scavenging by rain of atmospheric gases and particulates. *Atmospheric Environment*, 45(39), 7201-7217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2011.09.002>
- [19] Guaita R, Pichiule M, Maté T, Linares C, Díaz J. (2011). Short-term impact of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) on respiratory mortality in Madrid, *International journal of environmental health research*, 21(4), 260-274.
- [20] Halonen JI, Lanki T, Yli-Tuomi T, Tiittanen P, Kulmala M, Pekkanen J. (2009). Particulate air pollution and acute cardiorespiratory hospital admissions and mortality among the elderly, *Epidemiology*, 143-153.
- [21] Samoli E, Peng R, Ramsay T, Pipikou M, Touloumi G, Dominici F, Burnett R, Cohen A, Krewski D, Samet J, Katsouyanni K. (2008). Acute effects of ambient particulate matter on mortality in Europe and North America: results from the APHENA study, *Environmental health perspectives*, 116(11), 1480-1486.
- [22] Jiang XQ, Mei XD, Feng D. (2016). Air pollution and chronic airway diseases: what should people know and do?, *Journal of thoracic disease*, 8(1), E31.
- [23] Klaassen CD. (2013). editor, *Casarett and Doull's toxicology: the basic science of poisons*, New York: McGraw-Hill
- [24] Azad, A.K., Kitada, T. (1998). Characteristics of the Air pollution in the City of Dhaka, Bangladesh in Winter, *Atmos. Env.*, 32(11), 1991-2005.
- [25] Sattar, G.S., Uddin, N. (2005). Air pollution in Chittagong City, Bangladesh, *Proc. Internl. Conf. Environment Science and Technology*, 1-3.
- [26] Bangladesh Air Pollution Control Rules, S.R.O. 255-law/2022